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DENTAL MORBIDITY IN CHILDREN WITH DENTOGNATIC ANOMALIES

Abstract

The article analyzes the dental morbidity of children with dentognatic anomalies in Ukraine. The high prevalence of caries, periodontal and soft tissue diseases among this group of children is highlighted, and a statistically significant relationship between the presence of dental anomalies, bad habits and poor hygiene is established. Data are presented on the increased risk of non-carious dental lesions, functional disorders of the temporomandibular joint, and speech defects. Particular attention is paid to the impact of orthodontic treatment on the condition of oral tissues, in particular, potential complications when using fixed appliances.

Keywords: *dentognatic anomalies, malocclusion, dental caries, gingivitis, oral hygiene, enamel hypoplasia, orthodontic treatment, children, speech disorders, temporomandibular joint dysfunction.*

The problems of dental morbidity among children remain one of the most pressing in modern dentistry. Of particular concern is the high prevalence of dentognatic anomalies (DGA), which not only violate the aesthetics of a smile and the functional integrity of the maxillofacial system, but also create prerequisites for the development of concomitant pathologies [1-9]. Occlusion impairment complicates the chewing process, disrupts diction, contributes to the accumulation of plaque and the development of inflammatory processes in periodontal tissues. Patients with combined risk factors require special attention: DGA and bad habits, which significantly worsen the hygienic state of the oral cavity [10-15].

According to numerous literary sources, dentognatic anomalies are highly prevalent among children of different ages, and their frequency largely depends on the regional characteristics of the environment [4-20]. In particular, the results of a comprehensive examination of children aged 8 months to 17 years in different regions of Ukraine indicate a high incidence rate. According to Yanchuk O.Y., Skiba V.Y. (2019), the prevalence of dentognatic anomalies in children in Ukraine increased from 1960 to 2017: during the period of temporary bite - from 38.7% to

74.4%; variable bite - from 52.4% to 69.5%; permanent bite - from 45% to 76.3% [22].

These indicators clearly indicate the critical need for timely diagnosis of orthodontic pathology in preschool age. Early and accurate diagnosis allows for timely treatment, which, in turn, will ensure the harmonious development of the child's dentition and improve the quality of life.

According to the World Federation of Dentists (FDI), malocclusion can increase the risk of caries, periodontal tissue diseases, injuries, and complicate the functions of chewing, swallowing, breathing, and speech [6].

Given the high percentage of children with orthodontic pathologies and the widespread use of hardware-based treatment methods, studying the dental status of children with DGA is important for developing effective preventive and treatment strategies.

The purpose of the study was to analyze the current state of the issue of dental morbidity in children with dentognatic anomalies.

The condition of a child's teeth largely reflects the correctness of the anatomical structure of the maxillofacial area and the harmony of its functioning. The health of this system is not only an important

indicator of the general condition of the body, but also a key factor in the prevention of many somatic disorders. Pathologies of the maxillofacial region significantly affect not only physical health but also the quality of life of the child - his or her psychological state and social adaptation.

According to Smolyar N.I. et al. (2023), the prevalence and intensity of caries of temporary teeth in children with DGA is significantly higher compared to children without DGA. During the period of early intermittent occlusion, the value of the "kp" index in children with DGA is 21.89 % higher compared to children without DGA, $p < 0.05$, while in the period of late intermittent occlusion - by 47.01 %, $p < 0.01$ [18].

The determination of the enamel resistance test showed that children without dentognathic anomalies have a low level of structural and functional enamel resistance. Children with dentognathic anomalies have very low structural and functional enamel resistance. The worst indicators are observed in children with orthodontic pathology accompanied by bad habits [11].

The results of numerous studies confirm that in children with dentognathic anomalies there is a decrease in mineralization and enamel resistance, which leads to an increase in the intensity of caries damage to permanent teeth.

In children with dentognathic anomalies, changes in the mineralizing potential of the oral fluid are also observed. The average score is 1.8 ± 0.04 points, which corresponds to an unsatisfactory level. In healthy children, the remineralizing capacity of the oral fluid is higher and corresponds to a satisfactory level [11].

In addition, numerous studies have established a statistically significant correlation between the presence of orthodontic pathology and a high incidence of caries, periodontal tissue damage, and poor oral hygiene. This interdependence indicates a "mutual burden" [5-16].

Crowding of teeth, abnormal position of individual units of the dentition, distal and deep bite create favorable conditions for the accumulation of plaque. This is due to the formation of retention zones, disruption of occlusal contacts and insufficient functional load on individual teeth. As a result, the self-cleaning of enamel surfaces is impaired, which worsens oral hygiene and contributes to the development of inflammatory and carious processes.

In seven-year-old children with dentognathic anomalies, the hygiene index was 2.22 ± 0.06 points, which corresponds to a poor level of hygiene, while in children without pathology this index was significantly lower - 1.69 ± 0.07 points ($p < 0.001$), which corresponds to a satisfactory level.

The highest values of the hygiene index were recorded among children aged 9 years: 2.43 ± 0.05 points in children with dentognathic anomalies versus 1.81 ± 0.07 points in children without them ($p < 0.001$). These data once again confirm the importance of timely detection and correction of orthodontic pathology as a factor in improving oral hygiene and overall dental health of the child [21].

When studying the hygienic state of the oral cavity in children, taking into account the presence of dentognathic anomalies and bad habits, it was found that the worst indicators are observed in children with both of these factors. The best hygienic indicators are recorded in children without dental caries and without bad habits - both in the frontal and molar areas. Thus, dental caries and bad habits are significant risk factors for poor oral hygiene.

Marchenko K.V. (2011) analyzed the localization of plaque on different tooth surfaces. Most often, plaque layers were observed in the cervical region of the medial surface of the tooth and in the contact areas, as the least accessible for daily cleaning. This trend was observed in both boys and girls [15].

In children with crowded teeth in the anterior mandible, plaque was most often localized on the contact surfaces - $37.3 \pm 7.9\%$ of cases. In children with other forms of DGA, this figure was $31.1 \pm 8.3\%$, and in children without anomalies - $24.3 \pm 8.8\%$. Thus, with crowded teeth, plaque accumulation occurs most often in areas that are least accessible for mechanical cleaning - that is, on contact surfaces where toothbrush and toothpaste do not work effectively.

The situation with hygiene is especially unfavorable in children with both oral hygiene and bad habits. In this group of children, contact surfaces are affected by plaque in $42.4 \pm 7.6\%$ of cases, and combined plaque on the cervical area and contact surfaces - in $37.5 \pm 7.9\%$ of cases.

Deterioration of oral hygiene when wearing orthodontic structures is one of the key factors in the development of inflammatory lesions. This is due to the accumulation of microflora in the areas of the retention points of the appliance, mechanical irritation of the marginal periodontal tissues, as well as a decrease in antioxidant protection. The incidence of chronic gingivitis in such children is 81.2-84.1%, and caries - 87.8-92.9%.

In 30.5-32.9% of children with DGA, pathologies of the soft tissues of the oral cavity were recorded, in particular, mucosal hyperemia, decubitus aphthae, cheilitis, and allergic stomatitis due to wearing appliances. In addition, 39.5-40.9% of the subjects had non-carious dental lesions, including enamel hypoplasia (42.9%), hyperesthesia (9.6%), and wedge-shaped defects [11].

According to the results of numerous clinical examinations, more than a third of children and adolescents in Ukraine have dental anomalies. Occlusion disorders not only increase the risk of developing dental diseases such as caries and periodontitis, but also complicate the chewing process, which negatively affects digestion and food absorption. In addition, such anomalies have a significant aesthetic component, which often leads to psychological discomfort in children.

One of the leading methods of correction is the use of fixed orthodontic appliances, which is widely used in clinical practice. However, along with high efficiency, orthodontic treatment is accompanied by an increased risk of complications - from inflammatory processes in periodontal tissues to changes in the hard tis-

sues of the tooth and oral mucosa. Children with dentognathic anomalies are more likely than their peers with a physiological occlusion to have gingivitis and periodontitis with manifestations of alveolar ridge resorption, especially in crowded teeth and vertical occlusion anomalies [11].

Numerous studies have established a high prevalence of periodontal tissue diseases in DGA, ranging from 81.4-89.3% [15, 16]. Periodontal tissues are damaged in various types of malocclusion. Thus, according to various data, catarrhal or hypertrophic gingivitis is detected in deep (46.3%) and open (43.7%) bite, mesial (37.0%) and oblique (33.3%) bite [1, 5].

According to Marchenko K.V. (2011), dentognathic anomalies not only contribute to the occurrence of periodontal diseases, but also complicate their course due to poor hygiene and increased cariesogenic situation. In such cases, orthodontic correction is necessary. At the same time, hardware treatment also carries certain risks: additional retention zones for the biofilm are created, epithelial exfoliation occurs, mechanical pressure of orthodontic structures increases, and local immune defense and antioxidant activity may decrease [15].

In the process of orthodontic treatment, the crowns of teeth are displaced in the direction of the acting force. In the pressure zone, bone resorption is observed, while in the traction zone, apposition is observed. Such morphological restructuring is a long and dynamic process that continues not only during the active phase of treatment but also during the retention period. Since children with gingivitis or generalized periodontitis often have osteopenic syndrome, hardware intervention affects the altered bone tissue. This determines the specifics of the management of such patients and requires early, informative and non-invasive diagnosis of osteopenia.

Orthodontic treatment also affects the condition of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ). Functional disorders were detected in 4.7-5.4% of children: clicking, pain, restriction of mouth opening, zigzagging jaw movement, asynchrony of the TMJ heads.

The most pronounced functional changes are chewing disorders. Incorrect positioning of the teeth causes functional traumatic overload and impaired blood circulation in periodontal tissues [19].

In case of abnormalities and deformities of the maxillofacial area, nasal breathing is disturbed, which causes narrowing of the dental arch and changes in the nasal resonator. Literature data indicate the occurrence of mouth breathing as a result of infantile swallowing and impaired lip closure [6, 9]. Such children have disorders of voice timbre and difficulty in differentiating sounds in pronunciation.

Among the 462 children examined, 46.1% had speech disorders, and among children with detected anomalies - 55.3%. Most often, the pronunciation of whistling, hissing, and labial-dental sounds is affected, which correlates with the type of bite: in an open bite, whispering prevails, in a distal bite - articulation disorders [f], [c], in a mesial bite - distortion of anterolingual sounds [19].

The vast majority of speech disorders (79.25% of cases) occur due to a short frenulum of the tongue and defects in the dentition in the frontal region [14].

Conclusions. Dentognathic anomalies significantly worsen the state of oral hygiene in children, contribute to an increase in the intensity of caries and the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases. The combination of DGA with bad habits (finger sucking, tongue licking, etc.) increases the negative impact on dental health, in particular, causes an increase in the number of retention zones and makes it difficult to conduct effective hygiene.

Orthodontic treatment with fixed appliances can be accompanied by complications of the soft tissues of the oral cavity and deterioration of hygiene control.

Children with DGA are more likely to have speech disorders, functional changes in the TMJ, and non-carious dental lesions, which requires a comprehensive interdisciplinary approach to treatment.

Early detection of orthodontic pathology, informative diagnostics and implementation of systematic preventive measures are necessary to maintain dental health.

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